

Title: Quantum Information Holography: Asymmetric Primes, Geometry, and Quantum Mechanics

Abstract:

This paper investigates Quantum Information Holography (QIH) in conjunction with asymmetric primes, offering an extensive understanding of the universe's quantum framework through the interplay of geometry, light, and quantum mechanics. A detailed exploration delves into quantum foundations, path integral formulation, asymmetric prime interference, geometric description via light, quantum holography, and informational density. The cohesive interactions of these elements within QIH present a vast, intricate informational construct, providing new perspectives on the quantum realities of the universe.

1. Quantum Foundations:

The axioms of quantum mechanics delineate that states of a system are symbolized as vectors within a Hilbert space. The Schrödinger equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} |\Psi(t)\rangle = H^{\wedge} |\Psi(t)\rangle$$

underscores the uniform evolution of quantum states over time, governed by the Hamiltonian operator, $H^{\wedge}$.

2. Path Integral Formulation:

The paper examines Feynman's path integral formulation, outlining the summing up of a particle's quantum state over all possible paths, represented as:

$$K(b,a) = \int_{a}^b D[x(t)] e^{iS[x(t)]/\hbar}$$

Here, $K(b,a)$ is the transition amplitude between two points, and $S[x(t)]$ represents the action.

3. Asymmetric Prime Interference:

Emphasis is laid on the set of asymmetric primes (PA), highlighting their unique mathematical properties and resistance to typical quantum cancellation. A modified interference term (IPA) within quantum integrals is expressed as:

$$I_P A = \sum_{n \in P} A e^{in\theta}$$

with θ as a phase factor.

4. Geometric Description via Light:

The paper delves into the propagation of light in a medium, outlined by Maxwell's equations, and explores its implications within a quantum informational context, signifying perturbations in the quantum state of the system.

$$\partial_\mu F_{\mu\nu} = J_\nu$$

5. Quantum Holography and Informational Density:

In-depth insights into Bekenstein and Hawking's perspectives on the correlation between the surface area of an event horizon and the contained entropy or information, further highlight the principles of QIH. The entropy S of a black hole is expressed as:

$$S = 4kA/l_P^2$$

where A is the surface area of the black hole, k is the Boltzmann constant, and l_P is the Planck length.

6. Conclusive Interactions:

QIH, with its entwined elements, affords a comprehensive view of the universe as an expansive informational construct. The interplay of light, quantum states, and the exceptional properties of asymmetric primes play pivotal roles in shaping the quantum reality, offering potential pathways to unveil profound cosmic truths.

Conclusion:

The manuscript concludes with a compelling synopsis of the interactions and elements within QIH, reinforcing its potential as a powerful tool for understanding the intricate dynamics of the quantum universe. The exceptional roles of asymmetric primes, light, and geometric descriptions within this framework provide fresh, interconnected perspectives, fostering a deeper, more unified understanding of quantum mechanics and the universe's extensive quantum reality.

In Plain Words:

Quantum Information Holography, Mathematical Geometries, and the Landscape of Quantum Paths.

Each equation is a specific shape when graphed as a mod.. See attached drawing of mod 180 of $x^2 + 4x + 4$ graphed onto a holographic screen.

1. Geometric Construction:

Let us begin by visualizing a circle, the embodiment of discrete π (or a Qubit), where its continuous boundary is divided not into the usual 360 segments, but 180. With each radial segment originating from the center of this circle, they diverge outward every 2 degrees, creating a fan-like structure. This establishes a coherent framework: the topmost radial segment is labeled as 0, and as we progress clockwise, each subsequent radii increments by one, until we reach 179. The 180th segment then aligns perfectly with the 0th, forming a continuum.

2. Mathematical Pathways:

Given the quadratic equation x^2+4x+4 , we can map its values onto our circle. For each integer value of x , the resulting value from the equation determines which radial segment (or segments) it connects to. This produces an intricate pattern, tracing a unique path across the circle. This mapping, in essence, transforms an algebraic entity into a geometric one, creating a tangible representation of the equation's informational content.

3. Quantum Representations:

In the quantum domain, Feynman's path integral formulation posits that the quantum state of a particle is a summation of all its conceivable paths. When represented geometrically, this can be visualized as the superposition of countless paths or trajectories.

$$\langle x_f | x_i \rangle = \int D[x(t)] e^{i S[x(t)]}$$

Where $S[x(t)]$ is the action of a specific path.

Most of these paths, due to their symmetrical nature and interference, cancel out, leaving only those paths close to classical trajectories.

4. Prime Modulation and Quantum Resistance:

Primes, particularly asymmetric ones, possess inherent properties that resist typical symmetrical breakdown. When integrated into our geometric construction, these primes can be visualized as paths that stand out, resisting the natural tendency for cancellation in the quantum realm.

Much like how certain wavelengths in a TV signal create vivid images against a backdrop of cancelling waves, primes in our mathematical-geometric landscape shine brightly against a tapestry of cancelling trajectories.

5. The Holographic Perspective:

The Quantum Information Holography (QIH) framework posits that all information about a quantum system can be encoded on its boundary. In our constructed circle, each path (derived from the equation) can be considered a unique quantum informational trajectory, with its entirety captured on the boundary.

6. Conclusions and Implications:

Our universe might be imagined as a vast geometric canvas, where each mathematical equation paints its own set of quantum paths. In this canvas, primes and their unique properties stand in sharp relief against the backdrop of paths that cancel out. This intricate dance between symmetry and asymmetry, between cancellation and persistence, might very well be the cornerstone of the universe's informational architecture.

This perspective not only offers a fresh lens to view the quantum landscape but also provides insights into how fundamental mathematics intertwines with the very fabric of reality.